

A 53-Year-Old Man Who Underwent Living Donor Kidney Transplant Had Right Femoral Vein Thrombosis, Right Internal Iliac Artery Atheromatous Plaque, Ischemic Reperfusion Injury, Acute Kidney Injury, Septicemia, Septic Shock Due to *Burkholderia Cepacia*, Metabolic Acidosis, Adult Respiratory Distress Syndrome, Ischemic Heart Disease and Diabetic Autonomic Neuropathy: Multiplication of Drops!

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ABSTRACT

A 53-year-old man was on maintenance hemodialysis with right permanent catheter for 2 years because of non-functioning arterio-venous fistular (AVF). He had long standing diabetes mellitus with autonomic neuropathy. Right femoral vein and internal iliac vein were found to be thrombosed during living donor kidney transplant. Donor-renal vein was connected to right external iliac vein. Anastomosis of donor's renal artery to right external iliac artery was done because of atheromatous plaque at right internal iliac artery. Revision of venous anastomosis was done due to venous out flow obstruction noticed during ureter anastomosis. It resulted in longer total ischemic time, 45 minutes, and caused ischemic reperfusion injury. Intraoperative blood pressure varied 95/60 mmHg to 110/70 mmHg with two inotropes. It was complicated by septic shock, metabolic acidosis, adult respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), and acute kidney injury (AKI). Though antibiotics, triple inotropes, hemodiafiltration and ventilatory support were tried, the patient could not make it. Blood culture obtained 5 days after death revealed *Burkholderia cepacia*.

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KEYWORDS: right femoral vein thrombosis, right internal iliac artery atheromatous plaque, ischemic reperfusion injury, AKI in grafted kidney, septicemia, septic shock, *Burkholderia cepacia*, metabolic acidosis, ARDS, ischemic heart disease, diabetic autonomic neuropathy

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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is one of common cause of end stage renal disease (ESRD). Both macrovascular and microvascular complications were overt at the time of renal damage; the average duration was 15-20 years after onset of type 2 diabetes mellitus (Sauenram et al., 2023). Diabetic retinopathy and nephropathy were microvascular complications; and, they progressed simultaneously. On the other hand, ischemic heart disease, cerebrovascular accident, peripheral arterial disease and vascular calcification were related with macrovascular complication of diabetes mellitus (Hofer et al., 2026). Autonomic neuropathy caused undue tachycardia, postural hypotension, gustatory sweating, constipation, diarrhea, erectile dysfunction, and silent myocardial infarction (Varzideh et al., 2025). It also caused alteration in sympathetic response as well as parasympathetic response; impairment of heart and baroreceptor response during shock (Gogan et al., 2025).

In patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD), vascular calcification was frequently seen and it progressed with advanced CKD. Vascular calcification of median size arteries resulted in technical difficulties during vascular anastomosis: longer anastomosis time; anastomosis leakage; impairment in blood flow either due to atheromatous narrowing or plaque rupture; embolization of plaque; and cholesterol crystal embolization (Pyar et al., 2025) (Vascular Calcification Work Group et al., 2004) (Dube et al., 2021).

Kidney transplant is the treatment of choice for patients with end-stage kidney disease (ESRD). Maintaining adequate blood flow to vital organs during surgery is essential. Hypotension was common during general anesthesia. And intraoperative hypotension occurring after reperfusion in solid organ transplant attributed to additional ischemic injury in the graft (Adelmann & Legrand, 2024). In living donor renal transplant, the level of mean arterial blood pressure should be above 75 mmHg. When the blood pressure dropped during general anesthesia, treatment was based on optimizing preload using intravenous fluids and the administration of vasopressors. Either hypotension or failure to rise blood pressure to target level during surgery were caused by other issues: hypovolemic shock (occult blood or fluid loss); anaphylactic shock; cardiogenic shock (acute coronary syndrome or pulmonary embolism); drug induced vasodilatation (anesthetic drugs) and septic shock (Adelmann & Legrand, 2024). Intraoperative blood pressure

was related with acute graft function as well as delayed function (Goyal et al., 2025) (Pongpruksa et al., 2026).

Common induction agents currently used in renal transplant are anti-thymocyte globulin (ATG) or basiliximab. Among various ATG, rabbit ATG causes less hypersensitivity reaction than equine ATG. Anaphylactic reactions after initial exposure to Basiliximab was reported as rare event (Sasaki et al., 2007) (Barros et al., 2003). Insertion of chlorhexidine-coated central venous catheters caused trigger life-threatening anaphylaxis in susceptible patients undergoing renal transplantation (Ho et al., 2019). *Burkholderia cepacia* is a gram negative bacteria; its natural habitat is soil. And, it can survive in anti-septic solution. It was notorious for its multi-drug resistant nature (Lee et al., 2012).

Clamping time of artery and vein causes ischemia of solid organ; ischemic reperfusion injury (IRI). Ischemic time is related with graft function and outcome. Several studies supported that anastomotic time had significant impact on the development of both early and delayed graft function; and hence it should be minimized (Mahajan et al., n.d.) (Touffeeq Khan et al., 2019) (Montaigne et al., 2021). Ischemic reperfusion injury (IRI) is a natural process and it is unavoidable in renal transplant. Several molecular mechanisms were reported in IRI (Gulec, 2011) (Nieuwenhuijs-Moeke et al., 2020) (Savransky et al., 2006) (Chatauret et al., 2014) (Huang et al., 2025). During ischemia, cellular anaerobic metabolism releases nitric oxide, free radicals. Rapid release of these substances into circulation after longer clamping time results in hypotension, septicemia, acute kidney injury (Ponticelli et al., 2022) (Salvadori et al., 2015) (Fuquay et al., 2013) (Touffeeq Khan et al., 2019).

CASE PRESENTATION

A 53-year-old man had end stage renal disease (ESRD) due to diabetes mellitus and he was on maintenance hemodialysis for 2 years. At first, he had hemodialysis through right femoral vein for 6 weeks while he was planning for arterio-venous fistular (AVF). Then, left brachio-cephalic AVF was used for one year; and it became non-functioning. Thus, right femoral vein was catheterized again without success. Therefore, left femoral vein was catheterized and it was used for about 4 weeks. Later, permanent HD catheter was initiated to right subclavian

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vein. Before kidney transplant, he was doing hemodialysis with right permanent catheter.

His glycemic control was fairly good with linagliptin. His blood pressure was low normal; 95/60 mmHg to 110/70 mmHg. Therefore, he did not require anti-hypertensive drugs. He suffered neuropathic pain in both legs requiring pregabalin 75 mg twice daily. He did have neither postural hypotension nor undue tachycardia. Resting heart rate was 87/min.

Coronary angiogram was done as pre-transplant preparation though he did not have chest pain or dyspnea. It revealed 80% narrowing at left anterior descending coronary artery (LAD) and 90% narrowing at circumflex artery. Therefore, percutaneous dilatation and stenting was done 3 months ago. Echocardiogram showed LVEF 57% in post-stenting. He was on aspirin and clopidogrel.

For latent tuberculosis screening, blood QuantiFERON Gold Test for tuberculosis (IGRA) test was positive and anti-tubercular therapy was taken in July 2025.

Iliac doppler of right was done to detect vascular stenosis; and, it was normal. Carotids doppler was normal: normal intima media thickness; and, no plaque.

The donor was unrelated, young man 25 years old. He was healthy.

He had mild immunological risk as CDC cross match was negative. And basiliximab was used as induction agent. Immunosuppressive regime was steroids, mycophenolate mofetil and tacrolimus.

He was well prior to transplant surgery; blood pressure was normal (100/70 to 98/60 mmHg); pulse rate was 87/minutes; afebrile; no reaction to injection basiliximab.

Arrival to operating theater, blood pressure was 110/70 mmHg; heart rate was 82/minutes preoperatively. After induction of general anaesthesia, blood pressure became 90/65 mmHg with the heart rate of 60/minutes. Therefore, noradrenalin infusion (0.01 ug/Kg/min) was initiated immediately according to hospital protocol. In view of bradycardia and low left ventricular ejection fraction, dobutamine was added. Thirty minutes later, hemodynamic status became stable. Hence, noradrenalin infusion was tapered off and maintained with dobutamine infusion (2.5 ug/Kg/min). There was no undue bleeding from surgical site.

Retrieval of kidney from donor was uneventful though CT angiogram of donor demonstrated early branching of left renal artery with normal left renal artery, renal vein and ureter. Anastomosis of donor's renal artery to right external iliac artery was done as end to side fashion. And, donor renal vein was connected to right external iliac vein; it was found to be small in size (5 mm) fibrosed and narrowed.

First warm ischemic time was 2 minutes; cold ischemic time was 27 minutes; second warm ischemic time was 28

minutes; and total duration was 57 minutes. Focal areas of bluish discoloration and congestion were noted at the time of venous anastomosis; they lasted 1-2 minutes and disappeared spontaneously. And, after ureter connection by uro-surgeon, florid hematuria and poor venous flow were noticed. The grafted kidney became tense on palpation; possibility of venous out flow obstruction was considered.

Therefore, venous anastomosis of external iliac vein (10 mm) was revised immediately to its proximal part by vascular surgeon. Third warm ischemic time was 15 minutes; 72 minutes total (57 minutes plus 15 minutes). Intra-operative doppler revealed good flow; RI 0.5; segmental artery 0.6; minimal pelvicalyceal separation. Clamping time (2 plus 28 plus 15 =45 min).

Graft biopsy was done for several reasons: acute rejection; delayed graft function; transient appearance of patchy areas of bluish discoloration and graft congestion at the time of venous anastomosis; florid hematuria; and anuria. Then, hematuria was more pronounced; urine out-put during intra-operative period was 75 cc per hour.

In view of unstable intraoperative condition, patient remained intubated. Delayed recovery after general anaesthesia was observed. The patient was drowsy. Blood pressure was 90/70 mmHg. Pulse rate was 80/minutes. Endotracheal tube was maintained to give high flow oxygen. Arterial blood gas demonstrated metabolic acidosis; pH was 7.1; PaO₂ 65.6 mmHg; PaCO₂ was 33.6 mmHg; HCO₃ was 13 mmol/L. Hemoglobin was 12 g/dl. Hct was 36.0%. Sodium was 138 mmol/L; potassium was 5.3 mmol/L and calcium was 1.06 mmol/L. And, metabolic acidosis was corrected accordingly. Then the patient gradually regained conscious level an hour after surgery.

However, patient deteriorated further.

Possible hypersensitivity reaction to basiliximab, anaphylactic shock, was considered. Therefore, adrenalin was initiated; blood pressure rose to 120/80 mmHg. However, it reduced to 90/70 mmHg few hours later; cold and clammy extremities became pronounced.

Inotropes were increased to maximum dose. Antibiotics were escalated though there was no evidence of infection clinically. High flow nasal oxygen was given. Nonetheless, urine output was only 200 cc over 6 hours.

Renal replacement therapy was initiated 6 hours after surgery. ECG revealed sinus tachycardia. Echocardiogram showed global hypokinesia with LVEF 20%. The patient had acidotic breathing. Chest radiograph at immediate post-operative was normal. However, there were opacities at right lung suggestive of pulmonary oedema or ARDS, in CXR done 20 hours after transplant. He deteriorated gradually and expired 30 hours after surgery. Blood culture obtained 5 days after expiry showed growth of *Burkholderia cepacia*. Graft biopsy did not reveal rejection.

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DISCUSSION

In Myanmar, nearly one thousand pairs of living donor renal transplant have been done successfully since 1995. In our center, No (1) Defence Services General Hospital Mingaladon, we have been doing over 450 pairs of living donor renal transplant with 100% success (Hospital Statistics DSGH, 2026 May).

Regarding blood pressure in patients with end stage renal disease (ESRD), over 95% of them have hypertension. The blood pressure is usually very high, even refractory. Majority of them requires high dosage of at least 3 anti-hypertensive drugs. This patient did have low normal blood pressure (95/70- 110/80 mmHg); it was uncommon in patient with ESRD. The possibility of hypoadrenalism due to adrenal tuberculosis was considered; however, he did not have buccal pigmentation and his electrolyte pattern was not comparable with adrenal insufficiency. Salt losing nephropathy was unlikely.

From anaesthesia view, the target systolic blood pressure during renal transplant surgery is usually aimed at mean arterial pressure more than 75 mmHg to have good blood flow to kidney and vital organs. His systolic blood pressure dropped to 90 mmHg after propofol injection ie 10% drop from initial systolic pressure. And it was initially considered as normal response because 25% reduction of systolic blood pressure following anaesthesia was normal. Therefore, this patient required inotropes. Mean arterial pressure was stable at 80 mmHg.

However, second time drop of blood pressure following revision of venous anastomosis was probably due to ischemic reperfusion injury (IRI) and septicemia. Several reports mentioned the level of blood pressure during transplant surgery and its impact on graft kidney. Goyal et al suggested increased risk of delay graft function in renal transplant recipients if their mean arterial blood pressure was at 55 mmHg (intraoperative hypotension) (Goyal et al., 2025). Ischemic injury and denervation of the graft kidney impaired autoregulation of renal blood flow and renal perfusion was directly dependent on the systemic arterial pressure (Adelmann & Legrand, 2024). Therefore, the graft did not tolerate decreased arterial blood pressure in this case; and, it lead to acute kidney. Graft outcomes after kidney transplantation was significantly related with intraoperative hypotension (Adelmann & Legrand, 2024).

Blood supply to graft kidney would not be normal; several mechanisms caused poor renal blood supply to graft kidney. Increased intracapsular pressure and increased intrarenal vascular resistance of graft kidney attributed to impaired renal perfusion. Autoregulation of graft renal blood flow was diminished in the post-ischemic kidney (Adelmann & Legrand, 2024). Pongpruksa et al pointed out that prolonged exposure to intraoperative mean arterial blood pressure

(MAP) \leq 85 mm Hg was associated with delayed graft function (DGF) in adult living-donor kidney transplant. Both the duration of intraoperative hypotension and lower MAP determined postoperative DGF in living-donor kidney transplantation (Pongpruksa et al., 2026).

Adequate blood flow to vital organs during surgery is essential. In living donor renal transplant, the level of mean arterial blood pressure should be at least 75 mmHg; therefore, the inotropes are usually necessary. The protocol recommended fluid therapy and inotropes during anaesthesia. If blood pressure did not achieve the target level, addition of second inotrope was recommended. In this patient, blood pressure dropped to 80mmHg following revision of venous anastomosis. Failure to rise blood pressure to target level with fluid therapy and inotropes during surgery was caused by several issues: hypovolemic shock (occult blood or fluid loss); anaphylactic shock (drugs, cannula); cardiogenic shock (acute coronary syndrome or pulmonary embolism); and very rarely septic shock.

Although basiliximab was a potent induction agent with good safety profile, fatal anaphylactic reactions were reported as rare event (Sasaki et al., 2007) (Barros et al., 2003). Therefore, hypotension in this patient would be related with delayed anaphylactic reaction to basiliximab though bronchospasm nor urticaria was not evident clinically. Moreover, Ho et al found that insertion of chlorhexidine-coated central venous catheters caused life-threatening anaphylaxis in susceptible patients undergoing renal transplantation (Ho et al., 2019). Hypersensitivity reaction may be subclinical/asymptomatic; just production alloantibodies with overt reaction with succeeding dose. On the other hand, hypersensitivity reaction produces minor symptoms like urticaria, nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, diarrhea, tachycardia, mild fever and flu like reactions. The patient may have acute dyspnoea, stridor, bronchospasm, hypotension, tachycardia, sudden collapse and death. In this patient, anaphylactic shock was less likely.

The results obtained 5 days after the death of patient revealed significant growth of *Burkholderia cepacia*. It was resistant to cephalosporin, quinolone; and it was sensitive to aminoglycoside. The antibiotics given to this patient were according to antibiotic guideline in renal transplant; ceftazidime plus sulbactam. The question was ‘Where was the source of infection?’ Retrospective analysis after getting blood culture results (growth of *Burkholderia cepacia*) and acute rise in trend of total WBC count with neutrophilia favored possibility of septic shock in this case. Former reports pointed out *Burkholderia cepacia* as common habitant in hospital environment and it survived in antiseptic solutions (Gangaram et al., 2020) (van Laer et al., 1998) (Liao et al., 2011).

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In this patient, source of infection for *Burkholderia cepacia* was not identified yet. Therefore, *Burkholderia cepacia* sepsis would be another cause of acute kidney injury in this patient. Pathogenesis of septic acute kidney injury was said to be different from that of ischemia/reperfusion-induced acute kidney injury. Nonetheless, Lee et al proved a link between apoptosis, immune suppression, and the development of acute kidney injury during sepsis (Lee et al., 2012). However, Lian et al mentioned that ischemia-reperfusion injury affected intestinal microecology and these microecological changes contributed infection and rejection (Lian et al., 2024). Moreover, McHenry et al pointed out that septicemia was a common complication in patients having renal transplantation procedures; and it was associated with poor outcomes. Increasing age and comorbid burden were independent predictors of occurrence of septicemia (McHenry et al., 1976). In this patient, having *Burkholderia cepacia* septicemia, atherosclerosis, diabetic autonomic neuropathy, long warm ischemic time, acute kidney injury produced multiorgan failure and death; multiplication effect.

Though the patient was on inotropes and low systolic pressure, the patient did not have tachycardia. It was due to autonomic neuropathy which was not obvious previously. Having neuropathic pain in this patient which responded to pregabalin was strongly suggestive of neurologic involvement in diabetes mellitus. In this case, acute kidney injury of immediately placed allograft kidney was likely to be due to refractory hypotension; delay or unresponsiveness to inotropes; episodes of hypotension without undue blood loss; and bradycardia (Wang et al., 2012) (Gogan et al., 2025). Several findings highlighted that autonomic dysfunction was associated with the absence of a normal decrease or increase blood pressure at night; higher mean values of systolic pressure; blood pressure variability; and increased pulse pressure (Bushueva et al., 2025) (Pop-Busui, 2010). Moreover, damage of the autonomic nerves lead to dysfunction in heart rate control and vascular dynamics (Serhiyenko et al., 2023). Therefore, vascular dynamics in vascular anastomosis site of grafted kidney might not be normal; and it resulted in acute kidney injury in this patient. Vascular complications like intimal injury and dissection were reported to be one cause of acute kidney injury of allograft kidney (Haas et al., 2002) (Mayhew et al., 2022) (Lushina et al., 2019) (Goyal et al., 2025). However, there was no evidence of intimal injury in renal artery of transplant in this case.

Vascular calcifications were common in people living with hemodialysis and those with chronic kidney disease (Pyar et al., 2025) (Vascular Calcification Work Group et al., 2004) (Dube et al., 2021). And, they caused ischemia of small and median size arteries leading to ischemic heart disease and

cerebrovascular accidents. This patient did not have stroke; however, he had silent coronary narrowing in coronary angiogram. And, he underwent coronary balloon dilatation and stenting 3 months prior to transplant. He did not suffer chest pain or dyspnoea prior to coronary stenting; diabetic autonomic neuropathy. And D-dimer level was normal; troponin I was normal; ECG and echocardiogram did not reveal evidence of acute coronary syndrome or pulmonary embolism. Therefore, the acute coronary syndrome with cardiogenic shock was less likely in this patient.

On the other hand, in this patient, atheromatous plaque in right internal iliac artery was found only intraoperatively. The patient was only 53 years old; it indicated accelerating atherosclerosis in people living with hemodialysis (Pyar et al., 2025) (Vascular Calcification Work Group et al., 2004) (Dube et al., 2021). And, renal artery of graft kidney was connected with right external iliac artery.

Because of thrombosis and narrowing of right femoral vein, right external iliac vein was found to be small in size (5 mm) fibrosed and narrowed. It produced venous congestion of graft kidney, venous anastomosis between donor's renal vein to right external iliac vein was done twice. It further led to prolong ischemic time in this case. Finally, longer total ischemic time provoked/augmented acute kidney injury of graft kidney in this case. Total warm ischemic time was 45 minutes in this case; clamping time (2 plus 28 plus 15 = 45 min). Several findings had agreement on importance of ischemic time in renal transplant.

In renal transplantation, warm ischemia time is the interval from the removal of a procured kidney from ice storage to initiating graft reperfusion. Successful kidney transplantation depends on warm ischemia time. Shrestha et al analyzed the mean warm ischemia time among 230 renal transplant pairs. The mean warm ischemia time was 35.45 ± 7.35 min; the mean first warm ischemia time was 4.28 ± 2.05 min and the mean second warm ischemia time was 31.27 ± 7.04 min (Shrestha et al., 2023). This patient had longer warm ischemia time; 45 minutes. Several studies supported that anastomotic time had significant impact on the development of both early and delayed graft function; and hence it should be minimized (Mahajan et al., n.d.) (Toufeeq Khan et al., 2019a) (Montaigne et al., 2021). The impact of different vascular anastomosis techniques in renal transplant on outcome was mentioned in one study (Hernawan Rahmat Muharia et al., 2025).

Not only the cold ischemic time but also the warm ischemic time determined early outcomes of graft kidney (Marzouk et al., 2013) (Ville et al., 2021). It was observed that the anastomosis time >29 minutes was associated with delayed graft function (DGF); second warm ischemic time influenced early graft function and was significantly longer in patients with primary graft nonfunction (Kukla et al.,

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2016) (Roth et al., 2024) (Firat et al., 2025) (Khan et al., 2019) (Punia et al., 2023). In this patient, the anastomosis time was 43 minutes; venous anastomosis between donor's renal vein to right external iliac vein was done twice because of venous congestion of graft kidney. It resulted in primary graft nonfunction in this patient.

A strong correlation between the length of total ischemic time with a decrease in creatinine and urine production was proved in several findings. The longer the ischemic time, the lower the decrease in creatinine levels and the lesser the urine production (Nugroho et al., 2019) (Tennankore et al., 2016) (Lusito et al., 2021) (Mahajan et al., 2023) (Kukla et al., 2016b). It was clearly seen in this patient; he passed only 200 cc of urine over 30 hours.

Ischemia and reperfusion injury (IRI) is a complex pathophysiological phenomenon, inevitable in kidney transplantation; one of the most important mechanisms for non- or delayed function immediately after transplantation. Repair and regeneration process including cellular apoptosis, autophagy, and necrosis follows ischemia reperfusion injury. In addition to perfusion solutions and perfusion methods to minimize IRI, new therapies were underway (Gulec, 2011) (Nieuwenhuijs-Moeke et al., 2020a). Regarding the pathophysiology of IRI, Savransky et al pointed out alloantigen-independent activation (Savransky et al., 2006). Chatauret et al mentioned the rapid return to normoxia of graft kidney lead to a large burst of reactive oxygen species and dramatic reduction in antioxidant defenses (Chatauret et al., 2014). Huang et al emphasized mitochondrial oxidative stress and programmed cell death mechanisms (Huang et al., 2025). IRI was previously reported to be more frequent and severe in kidneys from deceased donors than in those from living donors. The pathophysiology of ischemia–reperfusion injury was complex: kidney hypoxia related to the duration of warm and cold ischemia; the harmful effects of blood reperfusion on tubular epithelial cells and endothelial cells; maladaptation repair; mitochondrial dysfunction; and acute rejection (Ponticelli et al., 2022) (Salvadori et al., 2015) (Fuquay et al., 2013) (Toufeeq Khan et al., 2019). IRI have been a natural step during kidney transplantation. IRI in this case also enhanced multiorgan failure. The long the clumping time to graft kidney would release more vasoactive substance (chemokines and cytokines) into the circulation. It caused vasodilatation, hypotension, metabolic acidosis, lactic acidosis, septicemia, toxic myocarditis, cerebral ischemia and ARDS in this case; multiplication effects. Longer warm ischemic time in this patient provoked ischemia–reperfusion injury in this patient. Several trials on substitute traditional preserving solutions with novel agents to dampen IRI were done (Zhao et al., 2018) (Ji et al., 2024). Steenvoorden et al tried peri-procedural administration of

alkaline phosphatase in living donor kidney transplantation to reduce IRI (Steenvoorden et al., 2023). Increased intracapsular pressure and increased intrarenal vascular resistance contribute to impaired renal perfusion. Autoregulation of renal blood flow is impaired in the postischemic kidney (Adelmann & Legrand, 2024).

Moreover, venous hypertension/obstruction of graft kidney was noted in this case, as evidenced by congested swollen graft kidney. And, it was corrected timely. Because of venous redo-anastomosis, the warm ischemic time was longer. In addition, longer clamp time to vessels led to reperfusion injury to graft kidney. It again produced cellular metabolic acidosis. And sudden release of vasodilators caused hypotension/shock; it provoked septicemia in this patient. And, it again augmented acute ischemic reperfusion injury and acute kidney injury of graft kidney. It was the explanation for oliguria/anuria in this patient. In addition, it resulted in metabolic acidosis, sepsis and ARDS in this patient (Ville et al., 2021) (Nieuwenhuijs-Moeke et al., 2020b) (Benjamens et al., 2020).

In summary, acute kidney injury of graft kidney in this patient was provoked by several factors: (1) long clamp time; (2) technical difficulties during vascular anastomosis; (3) prolong anastomosis time; (4) impair blood flow either due to atheromatous narrowing or plaque rupture; (5) embolization of plaque or cholesterol crystal; (6) metabolic acidosis; (7) fluctuating low systolic blood pressure; (8) poor sympathetic response in heart rate; (9) septicemia due to multi-drug resistant bug; and, (10) ischemic reperfusion injury.

CONCLUSION

Hypotension during living donor renal transplant is a challenging situation particularly in recipient with low normal blood pressure. Other features of anaphylactic shock may not be obvious except low blood pressure. Exclusion of cardiogenic shock and hypovolemic shock is essential. Septic shock is uncommon; however, it is likely in immunocompromised person even without fever or obvious source of infection. *Burkholderia cepacia* survives in antiseptic solution and it can cause fatal septic shock. . It is important to expect undue cardiovascular response in patients with autonomic neuropathy during hypotension and their response to inotropes may be variable. Vascular calcification in patients with ESRD result in technical difficulties in vascular anastomosis. It is important to predict femoral vein thrombosis on right side in patients with previous femoral puncture/catheter; it causes technical difficulties in venous anastomosis of renal allograft. Prolong vascular clamping time augments ischemic reperfusion injury, hypotension, metabolic acidosis, *Burkholderia cepacia* septicemia, shock, acute kidney injury and ARDS.

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Ethical consideration

Informed consent for writing case report was taken from patient's wife.

Declaration of conflict of interest

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REFERENCES

- I. Adelman, D., & Legrand, M. (2024). Intraoperative blood pressure management during kidney transplantation: Grafts under pressure. *American Journal of Transplantation*, 24(11), 1925–1927. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajt.2024.06.017>
- II. Barros, V., Rocha, V., Garcia, V., & Garcia, C. (2003). Anaphylactic shock after retreatment with Basiliximab. *Transplantation Proceedings*, 35, 579. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0041-1345\(02\)03406-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0041-1345(02)03406-1)
- III. Benjamins, S., van den Berg, T. A. J., Kuipers, T. G. J., Moers, C., Berger, S. P., Leuvenink, H. G. D., & Pol, R. A. (2020). Kidney temperature during living donor kidney transplantation is associated with short-term measured glomerular filtration rate – a prospective study. *Transplant International*, 33(2), 174–180. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tri.13528>
- IV. Bushueva, A., Korneeva, D., & Strongin, L. (2025). The influence of cardiovascular autonomic neuropathy on blood pressure profile in patients with a combination of diabetes mellitus type 2 and arterial hypertension. *FOCUS. Endocrinology*, 6, 6–11. <https://doi.org/10.62751/2713-0177-2025-6-4-01>
- V. Chatauret, N., Badet, L., Barrou, B., & Hauet, T. (2014). Ischemia-reperfusion: From cell biology to acute kidney injury. *Progrès En Urologie*, 24, S4–S12. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S1166-7087\(14\)70057-0](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S1166-7087(14)70057-0)
- VI. Dube, P., DeRiso, A., Patel, M., Battepati, D., Khatib-Shahidi, B., Sharma, H., Gupta, R., Malhotra, D., Dworkin, L., Haller, S., & Kennedy, D. (2021). Vascular Calcification in Chronic Kidney Disease: Diversity in the Vessel Wall. *Biomedicine*, 9(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicine9040404>
- VII. Firat, N., Karacan, A., Akın, E., Altıntoprak, F., Çelebi, F., Salihi, S., Kocatürk, E. M., Küçük, İ. F., & Dheir, H. (2025). Comparison of Double Renal Artery Anastomosis With Single Renal Artery Anastomosis in Kidney Transplant Recipients; Is There Any Effect on Graft Function? *Transplantation Proceedings*, 57(9), 1744–1747. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transproceed.2025.07.003>
- VIII. Fuquay, R., Renner, B., Kulik, L., McCullough, J. W., Amura, C., Strassheim, D., Pelanda, R., Torres, R., & Thurman, J. M. (2013). Renal ischemia-reperfusion injury amplifies the humoral immune response. *Journal of the American Society of Nephrology: JASN*, 24(7), 1063–1072. <https://doi.org/10.1681/ASN.2012060560>
- IX. Gangaram, U., Ramya, T., Jithendra, K., & Mohan, D. R. (2020). Burkholderia cepacia an emerging cause of septicemia, in an intensive care unit from a tertiary care hospital, Nellore, India. *International Journal of Advances in Medicine*, 7(3), 413–417. <https://doi.org/10.18203/2349-3933.ijam20200591>
- X. Gogan, A., Potre, O., Avram, V.-F., Andor, M., Caruntu, F., & Timar, B. (2025a). Cardiac Autonomic Neuropathy in Diabetes Mellitus: Pathogenesis, Epidemiology, Diagnosis and Clinical Implications: A Narrative Review. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 14(3), 671. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm14030671>
- XI. Gogan, A., Potre, O., Avram, V.-F., Andor, M., Caruntu, F., & Timar, B. (2025b). Cardiac Autonomic Neuropathy in Diabetes Mellitus: Pathogenesis, Epidemiology, Diagnosis and Clinical Implications: A Narrative Review. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 14(3), 671. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm14030671>
- XII. Goyal, V. K., Shekhrajka, P., & Mittal, S. (2025). Perioperative considerations in kidney transplantation: An anaesthesiologist's perspective. *World Journal of Transplantation*, 15(4), 107662. <https://doi.org/10.5500/wjt.v15.i4.107662>
- XIII. Gulec, B. (2011). Ischemia Reperfusion Injury in Kidney Transplantation. In D. (Md) M. Trzcinska (Ed.), *Kidney Transplantation—New Perspectives*. IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/18289>

A 53-Year-Old Man Who Underwent Living Donor Kidney Transplant Had Right Femoral Vein Thrombosis, Right Internal Iliac Artery Atheromatous Plaque, Ischemic Reperfusion Injury, Acute Kidney Injury, Septicemia, Septic Shock Due to Burkholderia Cepacia, Metabolic Acidosis, Adult Respiratory Distress Syndrome, Ischemic Heart Disease and Diabetic Autonomic Neuropathy: Multiplication of Drops!

- XIV. Haas, M., Kraus, E. S., Samaniego-Picota, M., Racusen, L. C., Ni, W., & Eustace, J. A. (2002). Acute renal allograft rejection with intimal arteritis: Histologic predictors of response to therapy and graft survival. *Kidney International*, *61*(4), 1516–1526. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1523-1755.2002.00254.x>
- XV. Hernawan Rahmat Muharia, B., Situmorang, G. R., Rasyid, N., Rodjani, A., & Birowo, P. (2025). Comparing anastomosis techniques on ischemia time in multi-arterial kidney grafts: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medical Journal of Indonesia*, *34*(1), 30–36. <https://doi.org/10.13181/mji.oa.257527>
- XVI. Ho, A., Zaltzman, J., Hare, G. M. T., Chen, L., Fu, L., Tarlo, S. M., & Vadas, P. (2019). Severe and near-fatal anaphylactic reactions triggered by chlorhexidine-coated catheters in patients undergoing renal allograft surgery: A case series. *Canadian Journal of Anesthesia/Journal Canadien d'anesthésie*, *66*(12), 1483–1488. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12630-019-01441-5>
- XVII. Hofer, G., Goode, S., Renström, F., Brändle, M., & Cavelti-Weder, C. (2026). Diabetes mellitus complications and their association with patient-reported outcome measures: A longitudinal study of the SwissDiab cohort. *Diabetes Research and Clinical Practice*, *236*, 113263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diabres.2026.113263>
- XVIII. Huang, A. J., Sharma, G. K., Parikh, R., Jin, Z., Darras, F. S., & Bergese, S. D. (2025). Molecular Mechanisms and Potential Therapeutic Targets of Ischemia–Reperfusion Injury in Kidney Transplantation. *Current Issues in Molecular Biology*, *47*(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/cimb47040282>
- XIX. Ji, J., Ma, Y., Liu, X., Zhou, Q., Zheng, X., Chen, Y., Li, Z., & Yang, L. (2024). Identification of Renal Ischemia-Reperfusion Injury Subtypes and Predictive Model for Graft Loss after Kidney Transplantation Based on Programmed Cell Death-Related Genes. *Kidney Diseases*, *10*(6), 450–467. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000540158>
- XX. Khan, T. F. T., Ahmad, N., Serageldeen, A. S., & Fourtounas, K. (2019). Implantation Warm Ischemia Time in Kidney Transplant Recipients: Defining Its Limits and Impact on Early Graft Function. *Annals of Transplantation*, *24*, 432–438. <https://doi.org/10.12659/AOT.916012>
- XXI. Kukla, U., Cholewa, H., Chronowska, J., Goc, T., Lieber, E., Kolonko, A., Budziński, G., Ziaja, J., Więcek, A., & Cierpka, L. (2016a). Effect of the Second Warm Ischemia Time and Its Components on Early and Long-term Kidney Graft Function. *Transplantation Proceedings*, *48*, 1365–1369. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transproceed.2015.11.042>
- XXII. Kukla, U., Cholewa, H., Chronowska, J., Goc, T., Lieber, E., Kolonko, A., Budziński, G., Ziaja, J., Więcek, A., & Cierpka, L. (2016b). Effect of the Second Warm Ischemia Time and Its Components on Early and Long-term Kidney Graft Function. *Transplantation Proceedings*, *48*, 1365–1369. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transproceed.2015.11.042>
- XXIII. Lee, S.-Y., Lee, Y.-S., Choi, H.-M., Ko, Y.-S., Lee, H.-Y., Jo, S.-K., Cho, W.-Y., & Kim, H.-K. (2012). Distinct pathophysiologic mechanisms of septic acute kidney injury: Role of immune suppression and renal tubular cell apoptosis in murine model of septic acute kidney injury. In *Critical Care Medicine* (Vol. 40, Issue 11, pp. 2997–3006). https://journals.lww.com/ccmjournals/fulltext/2012/11000/distinct_pathophysiologic_mechanisms_of_septic.10.aspx
- XXIV. Lian, Y., Li, P., Guo, Y., Tao, Y., Liu, Y., Liang, Z., & Zhu, S. (2024). Interaction between ischemia-reperfusion injury and intestinal microecology in organ transplantation and its therapeutic prospects. *Frontiers in Immunology, Volume 15-2024*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2024.1495394>
- XXV. Liao, C.-H., Chang, H.-T., Lai, C.-C., Huang, Y.-T., Hsu, M.-S., Liu, C.-Y., Yang, C.-J., & Hsueh, P.-R. (2011). Clinical characteristics and outcomes of patients with Burkholderia cepacia bacteremia in an intensive care unit. *Diagnostic Microbiology and Infectious Disease*, *70*(2), 260–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diagmicrobio.2011.01.008>
- XXVI. Lushina, N., Lee, A., Cuadra, S., Whang, M., & Sun, H. (2019). External Iliac Artery Dissection During Renal Transplantation: A Case Report and Literature Review. *Transplantation Proceedings*, *51*(2), 538–. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transproceed.2018.12.021>
- XXVII. Lusito, Nurani, A., Partiningrum, D. L., Arwanto, A., Lestariningsih, & Chasani, S. (2021). RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN WARM ISCHEMIC TIME AND RESISTIVE INDEX ON CREATININ REDUCTION RATIO DAY TWO AFTER LIVING KIDNEY DONOR TRANSPLANTATION. *Journal of Midwifery and Health Science of Sultan Agung*, *1*(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.30659/jmh.sa.v1i1.4>
- XXVIII. Mahajan, N., Heer, M. K., & Trevillian, P. R. (n.d.).

A 53-Year-Old Man Who Underwent Living Donor Kidney Transplant Had Right Femoral Vein Thrombosis, Right Internal Iliac Artery Atheromatous Plaque, Ischemic Reperfusion Injury, Acute Kidney Injury, Septicemia, Septic Shock Due to Burkholderia Cepacia, Metabolic Acidosis, Adult Respiratory Distress Syndrome, Ischemic Heart Disease and Diabetic Autonomic Neuropathy: Multiplication of Drops!

- XXIX. Mahajan, N., Heer, M. K., & Trevillian, P. R. (2023). Renal transplant anastomotic time—Every minute counts! *Frontiers in Medicine, Volume 9-2022*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2022.1024137>
- XXX. Marzouk, K., Lawen, J., Alwayn, I., & Kiberd, B. A. (2013). The impact of vascular anastomosis time on early kidney transplant outcomes. *Transplantation Research, 2*(1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2047-1440-2-8>
- XXXI. Mayhew, M., Solomon, R., LaGuardia, H., Shaw, K., Arenas, J., & Hranjec, T. (2022). Vascular Complications in Renal Transplantation: Surgical Salvage of Renal Artery Dissection. *Transplantation Direct, 8*(6), e1340. <https://doi.org/10.1097/TXD.0000000000001340>
- XXXII. McHenry, M. C., Braun, W. E., Popowniak, K. L., Banowsky, L. H., & Deodhar, S. D. (1976). Septicemia in Renal Transplant Recipients. *Urologic Clinics of North America, 3*(3), 647–666. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0094-0143\(21\)01139-3](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0094-0143(21)01139-3)
- XXXIII. Montaigne, D., Alhawajri, N., Jacquelinet, M., Coppin, A., Frimat, M., Bouyé, S., Lebuffe, G., Staels, B., Jacquelinet, C., & Hazzan, M. (2021). Day-Time Declamping Is Associated with Better Outcomes in Kidney Transplantation: The Circarein Study. *Journal of Clinical Medicine, 10*, 2322. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm10112322>
- XXXIV. Nieuwenhuijs-Moeke, G. J., Pischke, S. E., Berger, S. P., Sanders, J. S. F., Pol, R. A., Struys, M. M. R. F., Ploeg, R. J., & Leuvenink, H. G. D. (2020a). Ischemia and Reperfusion Injury in Kidney Transplantation: Relevant Mechanisms in Injury and Repair. *Journal of Clinical Medicine, 9*(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm9010253>
- XXXV. Nieuwenhuijs-Moeke, G. J., Pischke, S. E., Berger, S. P., Sanders, J. S. F., Pol, R. A., Struys, M. M. R. F., Ploeg, R. J., & Leuvenink, H. G. D. (2020b). Ischemia and Reperfusion Injury in Kidney Transplantation: Relevant Mechanisms in Injury and Repair. *Journal of Clinical Medicine, 9*(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm9010253>
- XXXVI. Nugroho, E. A., Hidayat, A., & Hidayat, A. T. (2019). Correlation of Warm and Cold Ischemic Time to Graft Function in Kidney Transplant: A Single Centre Report. *The Open Urology and Nephrology Journal, 12*, 66–71. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1874303X01912010066>
- XXXVII. Pongpruksa, C., Khampitak, N., Bunnapradist, S., & Xia, V. W. (2026). Intraoperative Mean Arterial Pressure in Relation to Delayed Graft Function in Living-Donor Kidney Transplantation. *Transplantation Proceedings, 58*(1), 45–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transproceed.2025.12.014>
- XXXVIII. Ponticelli, C., Reggiani, F., & Moroni, G. (2022). Delayed Graft Function in Kidney Transplant: Risk Factors, Consequences and Prevention Strategies. *Journal of Personalized Medicine, 12*(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/jpm12101557>
- XXXIX. Pop-Busui, R. (2010). Cardiac autonomic neuropathy in diabetes: A clinical perspective. *Diabetes Care, 33*(2), 434–441. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc09-1294>
- XL. Punia, S., Sadasukhi, N., Sadasukhi, T. C., Gupta, H. L., Gupta, M., & Sharma, A. (2023). To Compare the Effect of Warm Ischemia Time and its Significance, if any—Open versus Laparoscopic Donor Nephrectomy. *Indian Journal of Transplantation, 17*(4). https://journals.lww.com/ijjt/fulltext/2023/17040/to_compare_the_effect_of_warm_ischemia_time_and_d.9.aspx
- XLI. Pyar, K. P., Myint, A. K., Myint, M. Z., Shwe, W. K., Aung, Z. N. H., Maung, Y. H., Hlaing, S. W., Aung, S. M., LinMaung, N., Latt, C. N., Thant, M. M., Kyaw, S., Mya, T. M., Aung, W. L., Win, T. A., & Hlaing, O. (2025). Abdominal Aortic Calcification and Its Determinants in People Living with Maintenance Haemodialysis in 2 Selected Public Hospitals from Myanmar. *International Journal of Medical Science and Clinical Research Studies, 5*(11), 1797–1813. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijmscrs/v5-i11-01>
- XLII. Roth, N., Kalteis, M., Krause, A., Rösch, C., Huber, J., Enkner, W., Haller, M., Cejka, D., Függer, R., & Biebl, M. (2024). Vascular reconstructions in living donor kidney transplantation: A single-center experience over the last 17 years. *Frontiers in Transplantation, 3*, 1488277. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frtra.2024.1488277>
- XLIII. Salvadori, M., Rosso, G., & Bertoni, E. (2015). Update on ischemia-reperfusion injury in kidney transplantation: Pathogenesis and treatment. *World Journal of Transplantation, 5*(2), 52–67. <https://doi.org/10.5500/wjt.v5.i2.52>
- XLIV. Sasaki, H., Chikaraishi, T., Furuhashi, S., Tsutsumi, H., Miyano, S., Nakano, T., Sato, Y., Kimura, K., & Takahashi, T. (2007). Anaphylactic reaction after initial exposure of Basiliximab: Case reports. *Transplantation Proceedings, 39*(10), 3457–3459. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transproceed.2007.08.104>
- XLV. Sauenram, N., Sillabutra, J., Viwatwongkasem, C., & Satitvipawee, P. (2023). Estimation of the onset

A 53-Year-Old Man Who Underwent Living Donor Kidney Transplant Had Right Femoral Vein Thrombosis, Right Internal Iliac Artery Atheromatous Plaque, Ischemic Reperfusion Injury, Acute Kidney Injury, Septicemia, Septic Shock Due to Burkholderia Cepacia, Metabolic Acidosis, Adult Respiratory Distress Syndrome, Ischemic Heart Disease and Diabetic Autonomic Neuropathy: Multiplication of Drops!

- time of diabetic complications in type 2 diabetes patients in Thailand: A survival analysis. *PHRP*, 14(6), 508–519.
<https://doi.org/10.24171/j.phrp.2023.0084>
- XLVI. Savransky, V., Molls, R. R., Burne-Taney, M., Chien, C.-C., Racusen, L., & Rabb, H. (2006). Role of the T-cell receptor in kidney ischemia–reperfusion injury. *Kidney International*, 69(2), 233–238.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.ki.5000038>
- XLVII. Serhiyenko, V., Serhiyenko, A., Hotsko, M., Markevich, Y., Markevich, M.-Y., Segin, V., & Serhiyenko, L. (2023). Diabetic Cardiac Autonomic Neuropathy: Link between Heart Rate Variability, Violated Blood Pressure Pattern, and Pulse Wave Velocity. In M. E. Hernández Aguilar & G. E. Aranda Abreu (Eds.), *Topics in Autonomic Nervous System*. IntechOpen.
<https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.112894>
- XLVIII. Shrestha, K. K., Shrestha, P. C., Pradhananga, S., & Lama, S. (2023). Mean Warm Ischemia Time among Kidney Transplant Patients in a Tertiary Care Centre: A Descriptive Cross-sectional Study. *JNMA; Journal of the Nepal Medical Association*, 61(262), 519–521.
<https://doi.org/10.31729/jnma.8190>
- XLIX. Steenvoorden, T. S., van Duin, R. E., Rood, J. A. J., Peters-Sengers, H., Nurmohamed, A. S., Bemelman, F. J., Vogt, L., & van der Heijden, J. W. (2023). Alkaline phosphatase to treat ischaemia–reperfusion injury in living-donor kidney transplantation: APhIRI I feasibility pilot study. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 89(12), 3629–3636.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/bcp.15871>
- L. Tennankore, K. K., Kim, S. J., Alwayn, I. P. J., & Kiberd, B. A. (2016). Prolonged warm ischemia time is associated with graft failure and mortality after kidney transplantation. *Kidney International*, 89(3), 648–658.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.kint.2015.09.002>
- LI. Toufeeq Khan, T. F., Ahmad, N., Serageldeen, A. S., & Fourtounas, K. (2019a). Implantation Warm Ischemia Time in Kidney Transplant Recipients: Defining Its Limits and Impact on Early Graft Function. *Annals of Transplantation*, 24, 432–438.
- LII. Toufeeq Khan, T. F., Ahmad, N., Serageldeen, A. S., & Fourtounas, K. (2019b). Implantation Warm Ischemia Time in Kidney Transplant Recipients: Defining Its Limits and Impact on Early Graft Function. *Annals of Transplantation*, 24, 432–438.
- LIII. van Laer, F., Raes, D., Vandamme, P., Lammens, C., Sion, J. P., Vrints, C., Snoeck, J., & Goossens, H. (1998). An Outbreak of Burkholderia cepacia With Septicemia on a Cardiology Ward. *Infection Control & Hospital Epidemiology*, 19(2), 112–113.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/647778>
- LIV. Varzideh, F., Jankauskas, S. S., Mone, P., Kansakar, U., & Santulli, G. (2025). Autonomic neurotransmission in cardiovascular regulation and pathophysiology. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 19, 1739330.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2025.1739330>
- LV. Vascular Calcification Work Group, Goodman, W. G., London, G., Amann, K., Block, G. A., Giachelli, C., Hruska, K. A., Ketteler, M., Levin, A., Massy, Z., McCarron, D. A., Raggi, P., Shanahan, C. M., & Yorioka, N. (2004). Vascular calcification in chronic kidney disease. *American Journal of Kidney Diseases*, 43(3), 572–579.
<https://doi.org/10.1053/j.ajkd.2003.12.005>
- LVI. Ville, S., Lorent, M., Kerleau, C., Asberg, A., Legendre, C., Morelon, E., Buron, F., Garrigue, V., Le Quintrec, M., Girerd, S., Ladrière, M., Albano, L., Sicard, A., Glotz, D., Lefaucheur, C., Branchereau, J., Jacobi, D., & Giral, M. (2021). Timing of Kidney Clamping and Deceased Donor Kidney Transplant Outcomes. *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology: CJASN*, 16(11), 1704–1714.
<https://doi.org/10.2215/CJN.03290321>
- LVII. Wang, S., Randall, D. C., Knapp, C. F., Patwardhan, A. R., Nelson, K. R., Karounos, D. G., & Evans, J. M. (2012). Blood pressure regulation in diabetic patients with and without peripheral neuropathy. *American Journal of Physiology. Regulatory, Integrative and Comparative Physiology*, 302(5), R541-550.
<https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpregu.00174.2011>
- LVIII. Zhao, H., Alam, A., Soo, A. P., George, A. J. T., & Ma, D. (2018). Ischemia-Reperfusion Injury Reduces Long Term Renal Graft Survival: Mechanism and Beyond. *EBioMedicine*, 28, 31–42.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ebiom.2018.01.025>

A 53-Year-Old Man Who Underwent Living Donor Kidney Transplant Had Right Femoral Vein Thrombosis, Right Internal Iliac Artery Atheromatous Plaque, Ischemic Reperfusion Injury, Acute Kidney Injury, Septicemia, Septic Shock Due to Burkholderia Cepacia, Metabolic Acidosis, Adult Respiratory Distress Syndrome, Ischemic Heart Disease and Diabetic Autonomic Neuropathy: Multiplication of Drops!

Photo (1) Chest radiograph done 20 hours after transplant showing opacities at right upper zone

